

MILITARY PROCEEDINGS AND TACTICS OF AMIR TIMUR

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ANNOTATION: This article compares information about Sahibqiron Amir Temur's efforts to create a centralized state and his military campaigns on this path in various sources. The article also provides information about the structure and composition of Amir Temur's army, Sahibqiron's military tricks and tactics.

KEY WORDS: Sahibqiron, Amir Temur, Zafarnama, Ibn Arabshah, Claviho, fighting elephants, Tokhtamish, Yildirim Bayazid, Khoja Ilghor, Samarkand, Movarunnahr, Khorasan.

Many great figures have grown up in the Kashkadarya region where we live. The greatest among these figures is Sahibqiron Amir Temur, a skilled general and the founder of a centralized state. Many opinions have been expressed about Amir Temur.

The battle between Amir Timur and Yildirim Bayazid was brought to us by Claviho, Arabshah, Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi and other historians. Clavijo describes the battle in this way: Turks also with the city of Constantinople. After not being able to reach an agreement with Temurbek, both sides began to gather troops. Temurbek, who was more enterprising and successful in military work, gathered an army faster than Bayazid, hurriedly left Iran and came to the border of Turkey. He passed through the lands of Arsinga (Erzinjan) and came to the city of Sabastria (Sivos)[1].

In "Tuzuklari Temur" Sahibqiron gives an interesting example of internal intelligence in one of his poems: "Let the king be aware and vigilant of the people of the council, they often find fault and take it outside. They inform the ministers and emirs about the king's words and deeds[2]. For example, a similar incident happened with me, and several of my interlocutors on my own private wire were ministers and emirs and spies of Rome." Amir Temur explained the great importance of intelligence and counter-intelligence to the generations in his "Tuzuklari" with concrete real-life examples: "In the work of the state There are many bad people who destroy the enemies of the state and destroy its sacrifices with various tricks. For example, Amir Husayn tricked one of the ministers and the Romans, and said that he wanted to oppose me, Amir Idiku Temur and Amir Jokuni, the support and arms of my state. I sensed his treachery with my insight, so I didn't hear everything that was said about them"[3]

Rui González de Clavijo also provides information about the formation of Amir Temur's army. According to his information: The king has a kush that always accompanies him. It is structured in the following order: the army is divided among the chiefs. There are leaders who lead a hundred people, a thousand people, ten thousand people, and there is also a leader who is the leader of all of them. When this high-ranking commander wants to give an order for a unit to go somewhere, he calls these commanders to his presence, receives relevant information from them, and distributes the army according to his wishes[4].

On this day, elephants were chased by horses and people, and various interesting shows were shown. When they all ran together, the ground seemed to shake. Neither the horse nor any other animal can match the elephant in running[5].

Seeing these things with my own eyes, I became convinced of the idea that "one elephant can be equal to a thousand men in battle." Because the elephant walks through people and strikes both ways. And when the elephant himself is wounded, he moves quickly without looking back and forth, and fights even better. Because the elephant's very long jaw teeth are adapted for striking from a height, it is immobilized and a sword-like spear is installed for striking from below. Elephants can easily live without food for a day or two. It is said that he can even fight for three days without food [6].

In short, Amir Temur went down in history as the founder of a great state. The "Tuzukli Temur" compiled by him remained as lessons for generations. Its legacy was revived during independence. The fact that 1996 was declared "Year of Amir Temur" in our country is a clear proof of this. It should be an honor for us young people to learn more about the history of our great grandfather.

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